

Rural futures – the transition towards a circular society based on the harmonious coexistence of nature and humans: the case of RE:STORE in Satsumasendai City

Ryota Kamio

Ryota Kamio, Re:public, Inc.

Kagoshima, Japan

ryota@re-public.jp

Abstract

In the past decade, there has been a paradigm shift in promoting a more sustainable economy and society on a global scale. However, those policies are often designed for large cities like Tokyo and do not consider the context of rural areas. This paper describes the collaborative spearheading of a circular design lab, RE:STORE. The space was formerly a traditional rice shop that had been abandoned for the last decade in Satsumasendai City - a rural site in Kyushu. The renovation project was led by Re:public, a social innovation design firm based in the region that sourced bottom-up interventions and most importantly, placed local residents and its natural environment in the center of the transition towards circular society.

Satsumasendai's industry is currently dependent on its nuclear power plants, but due to a new government-mandated rule, the power plant may close down in the next 20 years. With such an emergent future of potentially losing one of its main sources of the city's industry, RE:STORE was born as a hub for the residents to learn, prototype, and explore new local economies and lifestyles by re-learning the relationship between humans and the natural environment. This paper describes how local residents were involved in the co-designing process of RE:STORE on both conceptual and practical levels. The project also adds to a greater discourse on how grassroots, bottom-up initiatives that prototype a lifestyle that is rooted in the harmonious coexistence of nature and humans.

Keywords

Circular design, Rural futures, Interspecies solidarity, Transition design

1 Introduction

Circular economy or Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are becoming a common goal in urban development and strategy. The global campaign of environmental awareness and sustainable development has helped cities set a new strategic plan to tackle such issues and improve our quality of life by rethinking the nature-human relationship. However, "our current systems operate under principles of occupation, control, and exploitation of lands and resources that once were in custody by others (Diez, 2020)". In other words, rural areas often provide their land or resources to sustain the cities in terms of energy and materials. Rural areas also have built their industries, mobility and urbanization processes to respond to such demands, due to the fact that such processes are thought to be the only way to survive in today's global capitalism.

In 2019, Satsumasendai City set a new strategic plan, *Satsuma Future Commons* along with Kyushu University, School of Design and Re:public with the aim of transforming into a circular city (referring to middle-sized rural cities). The city is located in rural Kagoshima prefecture, South Japan where a large

majority dedicate themselves to primary industries such as farming, fishing, and forestry; in many ways, they exemplify the possibilities of living in harmonious coexistence with nature. On the other hand, the city's industry is currently dependent on its nuclear power plants, but due to a new government-mandated rule, they may close down in 23 years. With the emergent future of losing one of the main sources of the city's industry, Re:public, a social innovation design firm based in the region renovated a former traditional rice shop. The rice shop was abandoned for the last decade and transformed into a circular design lab, RE:STORE for local residents to learn, prototype, and explore new local economies and lifestyles by re-learning the nature-human relationship. Our focus is sourcing bottom-up interventions and most importantly, putting the local residents and its natural environment in the center of the transition towards a circular society. This paper describes how citizens in Satsumasendai were involved in the co-designing process of RE:STORE on both conceptual and practical levels. This process was facilitated by community education and circular design practices by means of digital fabrication, open source technologies, and indigenous low technologies. Looking beyond technological advances, we have conducted a series of collaborative researches and workshops about local materials and indigenous knowledge and techniques. These include: fermentation, rice straws weaving, and bamboo craft. Moreover, RE:STORE has mapped out the local ecosystem and prototyped a circular city concept involving not only locally collected materials from the city's primary industry but also the craftsmen and artisan workers, and sometimes combining their experiences and techniques with digital fabrication tools to co-design the space. RE:STORE is in the early stage of its experiment, but it leads to a greater research and grassroots actions to explore and prototype how to form a new local economy and lifestyle; a lifestyle rooted in harmonious coexistence of nature and humans from the bottom-up perspective. This experiment demonstrates the effectiveness of place-based interventions and archiving the local wisdom for engaging citizens to participate in the further development of Satsuma Future Commons.

2 Background

Satsumasendai City is a municipality located in South Japan, Kagoshima prefecture with a population of approximately 90,000. It is a regular middle-sized rural city with general national issues like depopulation; however, what is unique about this municipality is that it has played an essential role in sustaining the energy supply in the region of Kyushu by means of 2 nuclear power plants, Sendai Nuclear Power Station (SNPS) installed in its coast in 1984/1985. SNPS has provided not only energy all over the region but also the municipality's infrastructures such as bullet train stations and highways. Local commerce such as hotels, restaurants, and leisure facilities were also developed for the growing number of engineers, researchers, and business people coming from outside the region to work for SNPS. Whether you're for or against nuclear power, SNPS has undoubtedly formed the local economical structure and largely influenced the lifestyles of the residents. However, after the 2011 Tohoku earthquake and tsunami in Fukushima a new government-mandated rule was set to limit the nuclear power station's lifespan to 40 years in 2012. Currently with the approval of the Nuclear Regulation Authority, it could operate beyond the 40-year limit for an additional period of up to 20 years after screening the company's safety measures for the unit. SNPS is going to face the limit in 2024/2025 and even in case of the extension of the additional 20 years, they're going to close down by 2044/2045. Therefore, unless the government changes its policies, Satsumasendai City will lose one of the most powerful engines of the local economy in about 20 years from now.

In 2019 Satsumasendai City set a new strategic plan, *Satsuma Future Commons* (SFC) along with Kyushu University, School of Design, and Re:public with the aim of creating an alternative industry and moreover, transforming into a circular city. The discussion began with the question about the use of a newly developed property of 240,000m² near SNPS which is located across the mountain and it has led to the creation of the innovation lab, SFC based on circular design principles after a series of dialogues and workshops with the city officials and citizens. Later SFC set the advisory board with experts in waste management, fashion, architecture, food, and design education and created working groups to narrow

down the concept to the actions in 3 areas: 1) Research & Development, 2) Community Development, and 3) Architectural design of SFC. Through each action in 3 areas, SFC set laboratories to foster research & development on the futures of fashion, food, and lifestyle along with its supporting systems and technologies and create a new local economy.

In 2022, Re:public renovated a former traditional rice shop abandoned for the last decade into a circular design lab, RE:STORE, for the citizens to learn, prototype, and explore new local economies and lifestyles in the city center. This is an independent project fully financed by Re:public (with no public money involved) and initiated as the first collaborative project with the citizens to explore bottom-up interventions. In other words, it is a starting point to challenge the 20th century's industrial model in which large capital is invested from outside the municipality to generate monoculture factories, power stations, etc... with the exploitation of lands and resources and the residents' belief in such growth. Satsumasendai city has often made such decisions rather in a top-down manner for the last decades; therefore it is also a challenge for the municipality to put the citizens again at the center of the transition toward an autonomous distributed and circular model. RE:STORE goes along with SFC's vision and its roadmaps but it puts special effort into facilitating hands-on learning about circular design thinking and co-designing with the residents in order to achieve the goals of SFC from a bottom-up perspective.

3 The development of RE:STORE

RE:STORE has been developed over 2 stages. The first stage comprised an investigation of bottom-up interventions in circular society and indigenous knowledge in the region, particularly local materials/resources and experts/craftsmen in cultures and activities that have lasted before the *Japanese Economic Miracle* (1954-1973). This phase initiated with rethinking the scope of circular design and discussing the role/position of RE:STORE in the transition toward a circular city under the Satsuma Future Commons strategy. An important revelation through the investigation is that the knowledge of indigenous lifestyles and the local techniques to support them that have been rooted in the place for ages have been overlooked in the discussion around circular design. This is troublesome given that many researchers in design theory address the need for a designer to intervene in socio-technical systems (Ceshin and Gaziulusoy, 2016). At this stage, our research reflects that in Japanese rural areas, indigenous knowledge and techniques are potential factors to transit from a globalized, industrial, and unanimous urban design to a local, participatory, and sustainable future. However, the potential of indigenous knowledge has been overlooked due to the lack of structured and visualized information. Therefore our first project at RE:STORE started with a series of collaborative researches exploring local materials such as bamboo, rice straws, regional distilled alcoholic beverage, Shōchū (Japanese: 焼酎) etc. This stage revealed that RE:STORE's principles are highly associated with the wide scope of Design for Sustainability (Ceshin and Gaziulusoy, 2016) including from 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) in the product-service system to the systemic and transition design, but at the same time it aims to explore outside the Western design framework by carefully observing the indigenous customs, relationality with the natural ecosystem, and the participatory process.

	Conventional Participation	Participation at RE:STORE
What is being participated in	Design projects	Local ecosystems
Who participates	Mainly citizens	Local collectives and industry-academia-government-private organizations
Objective of participation	Problem-solving	Rebuilding relationality upon the principals of interdependence and care
Outcome of participation	Universal solution for the majority	Interventions based on the locality
The role of design	Facilitation	Facilitation and catalyst (medium)

Table 1: Comparative definitions of "participation"

The second stage of the development was organized in the co-design/construction process of the space. The design and construction were conducted with local carpenters, craftsmen, and neighbors who had a deep understanding of the regional materials and ecosystem. The construction process revealed 6 crucial principals for bottom-up interventions in circular design: (a) **Research** about local materials, techniques, and ecosystem; (b) **Unpacking** their "usual" materials and techniques; (c) **Speculating** them for different purposes; (d) **Contextualizing** in ecosystemic level; (e) **Material-driven prototyping**; and (f) **Archiving** the process and outcome. In fact, the repurposing and reimagining of local materials and knowledge fosters community engagement and participation; the design process becomes a much more active, democratic process. This contrasts the hierarchical process where decision-making is often led by the designers rather than residents.

Figure 1: Place-based participatory approach to circular design

While how participants are involved in the co-design process may change, it also revealed that the role of design/designers changes according to each part of the process. For example, from (a) to (d) the role of

RE:STORE is rather a catalyst that stimulates new perspectives, unpacks the conventional way of thinking, and promotes putting the existing knowledge in the transition process for a circular society. Thanks to the growth of Fab lab/Makers movement the design community is in a new period of intervention. Emergent distributed technological tools, often low-cost or even DIY tools, such as digital fabrication and DIY bio kits facilitate the interventions in pre-existing ecosystems. The interventions offer different perspectives and prototypes for different purposes or meanings in our ecosystem. The construction process of RE:STORE is a combination of indigenous knowledge and those digital and technological tools to prototype possible and most importantly, desirable artifacts of the citizens in the municipality's transition toward a circular city.

4 The application of the place-based participatory approach

RE:STORE has conducted a series of community education programs, collaborative research, and workshops during the development of the space by the approach explained above. Here we report some of the interventions that have been carried out in each step.

4.1 Research about local materials, techniques, and ecosystems

DIY Bio research

This is collaborative research about understanding the local ecosystem from a biological perspective by means of biotechnology. Biotechnology has made rapid progress over the last decade and become emergent technology in agriculture, medicine, pharmaceuticals, and energy. As explained above, in Satsumasendai city a large majority dedicate themselves to primary industries so biotechnology has always been familiar in their industry. In fact, it is one of the largest testbeds of such technology in the country. Also, in their everyday life fermentation, one of the most ancient biotechnologies, has been practiced over generations. This project was the initial stage to research on the harmonious coexistence of nature and humans firstly by understanding our current ecosystem and the low technologies that we have used to interact with nature. The 1st workshop was carried out following open source protocol, [Open Yeast Protocol](#) by YCAM Interlab (Yamaguchi Center for Arts and Media), and prepared DIY Bio kits with kitchen utensils. Later we collected wild yeast in *Nitta Shrine*, the oldest shrine in the municipality where the purest natural ecosystem remains, and then cultured, observed, and preserved the yeast in the growth medium made of regional potatoes. In the 2nd workshop, we researched fermentation techniques that have been preserved in the region and tried to make *miso* with the wild yeast found in nature (but it failed for safety reasons).

Image 1: Collection of wild yeast in *Nitta shrine* (left) and the preparation of hand-made *miso* (right)

This project was kicked off with the aim of learning the fundamental consideration, multi-species and interdependence, among the citizens for the circular transition. This research about the local ecosystem by means of emergent technologies revealed points of intervention in the existing ecosystem and most importantly, the ethics to lead to greater research and development.

4.2 Unpacking "usual" materials and techniques

Creative repair

Creative Repair (CP) is a series of workshops run by local carpenters and craftsmen in which we bring waste or unused furniture from each household to creatively repair for different purposes. It began with unpacking the furniture with our hands to understand the existing assembly system and the materials used. In order to understand better, we also made comparisons of the parts and materials among the same furniture but from different brands. This unpacking process helps us understand how the brands try to organize their business models by looking at the quality of materials used in hidden parts or the designed induction to consume other products of them. More importantly, we often came to the conclusion that those parts and materials are not designed for reuse or repair, at least not with our own hands. CP intends to unpack the existing system and tries to prototype circular product services which should be easily reused and recycled.

Image 2: Unpacking a wasted chair (left) and a prototype to replace broken chair seats (right)

Also, it plays a role as a community education platform for the citizens to learn a variety of skills from traditional tools of carpenters to digital fabrication, and most importantly, to share the knowledge and techniques among the participants. By unpacking such usual materials and techniques we aim to seek their possible applications for circular product-service design and creative civic participation model in a circular society.

4.3 Speculating them for different purposes and (e) Material-driven prototyping

Tatami chair making

Since the construction phase of RE:STORE, the planning team was intentional about inviting to community members who had unused or waste materials to come and talk with them. We're located in the center of the municipality but still, many manufacturing and retail facilities remain and one of them is the *Tatami* factory and shop; a tatami (*Japanese: 畳*) is a type of mat used as a flooring material in traditional Japanese-style rooms. In the process of tatami making many pieces are abandoned and piled up in the factory or go to waste. In this workshop it was important to "escape" from the conventional way of thinking and production model to imagine the creative use of the materials, therefore firstly we mapped out the characteristics of tatami and experimented with them in as many ways as possible using our five senses. Later in the ideation process, we shared ideas for our desirable uses including speculative ones and prototyped possible applications.

Image 3: Ideation with *tatami* waste (left) and a prototype; *tatami* chairs (right)

Rice straws weaving

Sendai Great Tug-of-War festival (*Japanese: 川内大綱引き*) is a 420 years-old tradition of Satsumasendai City since 1600 and a part of the tradition is to make a tug of 365m x 40cm with the weight of 7t made of rice straws with approximately 1,500 residents only for 7 hours. Therefore, the majority of the citizens have great skills in weaving rice straws. This is an extended project from *Creative Repair* to explore applications of indigenous technology and experience in a circular design. After days of "dialogue" with rice straws, the material's characteristics like the fiber found during the experimentation phase led to prototyping lampshades with unused hangars from the member's house.

Image 4: Material exploration (left) and a prototyped lampshade (right)

Through these steps we aim to learn and prototype circular design from a material perspective by exploring yet unfamiliar and unusual "things" (not considered as materials yet), in particular locally known materials such as the ones used in local industry or traditional festival for a large amount. It's a starting point to design emerging circular materials such as biodegradable plastic and think carefully about their sustainable production by considering the local ecosystem and environmental impact.

4.4 Contextualizing in ecosystemic level

Bamboo is the most iconic natural resource for Satsumasendai City with the largest bamboo forests in the country and it has a tight relationship with the local artisan of bamboo craftwork. However, for the last decades bamboo as a material for everyday items has been substituted by plastic and the bamboo work industry has radically shrunk too. For that reason, many bamboo forests are abandoned, and given its active propagating power bamboo consumes nutrition materials ahead of other species, which has led to an ecosystemic collapse in the region.

We kicked off the bamboo architecture project with Kyushu University, School of Design to research about the ecosystem of bamboo forests and its architectural application based on the harmonious co-existence with the local ecosystem and circularity. Currently, we're in the investigation phase re-thinking the artisan infrastructures installed in the region and their unique network.

Image 5: Fieldwork in the bamboo forest (left) and a customized kiln for bamboo in the region (right)

This project is an ecosystemic intervention facilitated through local fabrication with locally sourced materials and careful calibration of a balanced production-consumption chain from the environmental point of view, rather than a market-driven one. It aims to define proper industrial size and growth based on the local ecosystem and make a circular architectural model.

5 Conclusion and next steps

In this paper, we have presented the initial stage: of a civic circular design lab, RE:STORE relating to the municipality's transitional strategy of Satsuma Future Commons toward a circular society in rural Japan. We developed the framework of 6 steps in order to transform into a circular city from a bottom-up perspective putting the citizens and nature in the center, which involves community groups, organizations, and governments to guide civic engagement to tackle environmental issues. During the vision making, we studied several design theories and practices, particularly circular design, participatory design, and transition design, and we came to the conclusion that often indigenous low technologies and local wisdom are overseen in such discourse. While public institutions take an institutional approach, it is crucial to think about how and with what tools the citizens intervene to prompt a circular transition. This involves prototyping a new local economy and lifestyle and unpacking existing local tools and indigenous knowledge regarding living in coexistence with nature.

The next steps for RE:STORE will be the governance of such interventions. RE:STORE is already shifting to the next stage; in order to create a future commons, it is essential to continue to think about who will govern and how to govern.

References

- Balestrini, M., Rogers, Y., Hassan, C., Creus, J., King, M., Marshall, P. (2017) A City in Common: A Framework to Orchestrate Large - scale Citizen Engagement around Urban Issues. CHI2017, May 6–11, 2017, Denver, CO, USA.
- Ceschin, F. and Gaziulusoy, I. (2016) Evolution of design for sustainability: From product design to design for system innovations and transitions, *Design Studies* Volume 47, Pages 118-163.
- Diez, T. (2020) Understanding what it means to design for emergent futures, *Making Futures: 2020 International Research Conference*. Plymouth College of Art, Plymouth, UK.
- Dunne, Anthony (2013). *Speculative everything: design, fiction, and social dreaming*. Fiona Raby. Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA.
- Hill, D. (2022) *Designing missions Mission-oriented innovation in Sweden— A practice guide* by Vinnova, Stockholm, Sweden.
- Moreno, M.; De los Rios, C.; Rowe, Z.; Charnley, F. (2016) A Conceptual Framework for Circular Design. Sustainability, Centre for Competitive Creative Design (C4D), Cranfield University, College Road, Cranfield MK43 0AL, UK.
- Nancy M. P. Bocken, Ingrid de Pauw, Conny Bakker & Bram van der Grinten (2016) Product design and business model strategies for a circular economy, *Journal of Industrial and Production Engineering*, 33:5, 308-320.

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- R. Arnstein (1969) A Ladder of Citizen Participation, *Journal of the American Planning Association*, Vol. 35, No. 4, pp. 216-224.
- T. Irwin, C. Tonkinwise, G. Kossoff. (2020) *Transition Design: An Educational Framework for Advancing the Study and Design of Sustainable Transitions*, Cuadernos del Centro de Estudios de Diseño y Comunicación, Fundacion Universidad de Palermo, Buenos Aires, Argentina.